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AN INTRODUCTION TO POLITICAL INSTITUTIONS OF APATANI TRIBE OF ARUNACHAL PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

Apatani Tribe dwells in the picturesque Valley of Ziro in Lower Subansiri district of Arunachal Pradesh. The tribe is known for their tattooed face and wet rice cultivation. The paper will deal with origin of the political institution called Bulliangs in maintaining peace and tranquility within the tribe. It also throws light on various categories of Bulliangs, their distinct roles and their relevance in the society.)

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The Apatanis living in Ziro Valley remained isolated from rest of the world for a pretty long period. As the tribe did not have a script, their socio-economic and political life is reconstructed from their oral traditions. The oral tradition of the Apatanis comprises of: (a) Mijih (b) Ayu (c) Barih (d) Migung. All these oral tradition contains historical material. Mijih is the storehouse of all religious verses used for performances of rites and rituals. It deals with good memory of their mythic legendary past, origin and functions of different socio-political institution, genealogy and the explanations need for them. Ayu and Barih are the expression of the Mijih. Migung are more historical which are narrated in prose that deals about various events and precedents of war, socio-political alliance, epidemics, fire accidents, natural calamities, political institutions and arbitration of various disputes. Hence the political history of the Apatanis can be well understood and reconstructed through the oral tradition of Migung.

Origin of political institution:

The elderly Apatanis says that Mijih and Migung have originated at the period and place along with the origin of the tribe. The priest refers that both Mijih and Migung had its origin at Ipyo Supung (Origin place of Apatani Settlement) under the guidance of legendary man called Ipyo Popi or Kolyung Popi. They quote that “Miyu Saling La Gyunyang Santa, Tiigo Santa Du” which means, a man is born with religious rites and ceremonies². For them a man can’t live a prosperous and healthy life without the performance of religious rites and rituals. Similarly, as a man is also born with disputes and controversies, the political institution and mechanism of arbitration must have originated with the origin of the tribe. The socio-religious practices and the political institution are the inseparable elements of the tribe. When the political arbitration is unable to deliver justice, then supernatural justice is sought since time immemorial. The arbitration of the Apatanis is based on the precedent derived from their ancestors. The Apatanis says that “Aba-Apa Ka Nitting Horming Doko Ho” (what we follow is the footprint of our ancestors). Hence, the Nitting Horming (Proverbs) is the basis of the customary laws for the tribe.

The first ancestor of the Apatanis was Abotani. The myths say that series of Abotani was born out of same lineage and Neya Tani was last amongst them. The literary meaning of Neya meant “mankind” and Tani meant “name and race”. The political institution of Apatanis is also termed as Neya Bulliyang where Neya meant “mankind” and Bulyang meant “political institution”. As the term Neya is prefixed for the ancestor of Apatanis and the political institution, perhaps both mankind and the political institution might have evolved simultaneously at the same period of their origin.

The another myth refers that the creator of the universe created the first priest of Apatanis called Kolyung Bumya Nyikang in order to mediate various spirits and deities. The priest in order to mediate the spirits and deities under the guidance of Kolyung Popi evolved the rituals of Gri and Yachu etc. In fact these rituals are performed to appease the spirit of disputes and controversies. Besides, the Neya Bulliangs (political Institution) have very vital role in almost all the socio-religious ceremonies. The oral tradition depicts that when society was evolved, it turned into chaos and disorder due lack of established customary laws and means of arbitration. Therefore, it can be presumed that origin of (Neya Bulliang) political institution evolved before the creation of priesthood to settle their disputes supernatural powers. Hence, the term Neya Bulliang can be understood in the following definitions:

- The Neya Bulliang is the democratic body and representative of the village or clan to settle civil and criminal cases which has its genesis from time immemorial.
- The Neya Bulliang is the institution with political, social, and religious responsibility that is endowed by both supernatural entity and mankind.
- The Neya Bulliang is the highest authority of socio-political and judicial administration in Apatani society.
- The Neya Bulliang acts as representative of public opinion and the upholder of customary laws in Apatani Society.

Every specified clan of the seven major villages of Apatani valley has a Neya Bulliang member to represent their clan. The Neya Bulliangs of Apatani Valley are divided into two groups namely (i) Nichi-Niti, Reru-Tazang, Dire Hija Buliang (Tiini Aso) (ii) Diibo, Hari and Tailyang Hao Buliang (Diibo Aso). The former Buliang is composed of members from Hong, Reru, Tazang and Hija Villages. The latter is composed of members from Hari, Tailyang-Kalung, Dutta, Mudang-Tage and Bamin-Michi Villages. The division of Neya Bulliang was not sanctioned with its origin but evolved on the basis of conflicts amongst the Apatani Villages. The division of the Neya Bulliangs arose from the Supung Chambyo (Apatani Valley war) on the issue of Tappo Yalu (Collection of Thatch used for Roofing the house). During this dispute and war the whole Apatani valley was allied into above mentioned group to defend and support their allies.

The membership of Neya Bulliang is a permanent body and inherited by the heir on hereditary basis. As the post of Neya Bulliang is ordained by the supernatural power and will of the society. Therefore common people of the Apatani society can never ever become a member of Neya Buliang. This post is transferred from one generation to another on hereditary basis. The Neya Buliang's father nominates his son having adequate knowledge on customary laws and arbitration. Normally, the eldest son is nominated to this post. However, there is no binding that the post should only be inherited the eldest son since the nomination depends on the discretion and capability of his son. Even the youngest son can inherit this post. If a Neya Bulliang does not have a son to inherit then the post of Neya Buliang transferred to the nearest cousin for inheritance. In general practice the post of Neya Buliang was never held by women but there is no restriction isolating the woman from becoming a Neya Buliang. But if a Neya Bulliang dies when his son is a minor, in that case the mother holds the post and performs all the functions of the post till the minor becomes an adult. As soon as the child becomes adult to participate in all the proceedings of the Neya Bulliang the mother transfer the post to her child.

Since the post of Neya Buliang was very prominent and noble post for both spiritual being and mankind, often there use to be tussles amongst the sons or cousins if there is no son for succession to the post of Neya Bulliang. Sometimes the tussle for succession becomes very intensive leading to physical and materialist contest amongst the contender. However, the essential qualities to become a Neya Bulliang are as follows:

- a) He should have good command over the customary laws.
- b) He should be a good orator to arbitrate the disputes.
- c) He should have good humor and presence of mind.
- d) He should also have adequate knowledge on religious rites for functioning religious role.
- e) Above all he should be mentally and physically fit to attend every works.

There are four categories of Bulliangs comprising of (i) Neya Bulliang (ii) Kiimer Buliang (iii) Kiidi Bulliang and (iv) Mudo Bulliang. The Neya Bulliang is first category of Bulliang which is further is divided into three categories namely Akha Bulliang, Yapa Bulliang and Ajang Bulliang based on the age groups. The Akha Bulliangs are the most matured and aged members of Neya Bulliang, who are always consulted and kept, informed about every event and progress of disputes if arises in society. The vital decision and proclamations on the arbitrations are pronounced by them.

The Yapa Bulliangs are the middle aged member who swiftly carries the daily affairs of village and inter-village administration independently or on advice of the Akha Bulliangs. The Yapa Bulliang is also previously called as Miha Bulliang (Assistant of Neya Bulliang). The institution of the Yapa Bulliangs was necessary as the Akha Bulliangs with their old age could not swiftly move from one village to another to settle disputes as when called far.

The Ajang Bulliangs are comparatively young members who acted as messengers and coordinated the two former Bulliangs during the crises in the Apatani valley.

The Apatanis considers that the classification of the Neya Bulliangs never existed since the origin of the

mankind. For them the Akha Bulliangs are the original Neya Bulliangs that was transferred from time immemorial. It is said that Yapa Bulliangs and the Ajang Bulliangs are newly incorporated Neya Bulliangs who were nominated to diffuse the war in Apatani Plateau (Supung Chambyo) in early 1940s.

The second category of Bulliang is as old as the Neya Bulliang that had originated during same period. Every clan has their own member of Kiidi Bulliang. The role of this institution is religious in nature. They perform funeral ceremonies of disposing the dead body. The funeral functions of Kiidi Bulliang comprises of preparing the grave, burying the corpse, fixing of funeral structure over the grave, fixing skull of sacrificed animal on the funeral structure, feeding the food at the funeral structure for the dead, fetching of water for funeral ceremony, preparation of food for the deceased family during the funeral taboo period and throwing away of urn during purification ceremony of funeral ritual. This people have to rigidly observe the taboo's of 10 days confinement within the house in case of accidental death. The posts of Kiidi Bulliang are occupied from the Gyuchi clan (plebeian) and never from Gyuth clan (patrician). Due to their unique service for the society, they occupy very prominent position in the society especially during funeral ceremonies. During their leisure time they live their normal life. These peoples are entitled to receive husked rice, meat of sacrificed meat called Arna (Chest portion) during the socio- religious ceremonies in recognition of their service rendered towards the society.

The third category is also as old as the Neya Bulliang that had its origin during same period. The role of this institution is religious in nature. The function of the Kiimer Bulliang is to castrate the male domestic pig that is sacrificed in the religious ceremonies. The Apatani oral tradition reveals that sacrifices of non-castrated pig cannot appease the spirit and deities for whom the sacrifices are made. Therefore, the society nominates and entrust the task of castration to a women who is skilled in such work. In fact work of castration is considered to be of below dignity work by the common people and they were considered religiously untouchable. They are forbidden from entering the house of solemniser during socio-religious ceremonies. However, such restriction does not apply to the family members of Kiimer Bulliang. It is ambiguous whether this post was hereditary in nature. This post is never held by the patrician family (Gyuth) or plebeian family (Allo Gyuchi) descendent. The post was usually occupied by the immigrant slaves who are incorporated into family of plebeian. For their selfless service, the society reciprocates them by constructing their house along with presentation of meats during

Again the fourth category is also as old as the Neya Bulliang that had its origin during same period. The role of this institution is religious in nature to perform socio-religious ceremony for bumper agricultural harvest and social harmony. A member from every clan of Apatani Village nominated for the conduct said ceremonies and they are called as Miido Bulliang. They are also often called as Goras. They are considered intermediately between supernatural power and mankind. These people manage the requisite materials for the conduct of agricultural ceremonies like Dree, Yapung, Chandi-Metii, Myokung, Tamu, and Sii-Myoro. Besides, they also perform rituals for the protection from epidemics within the settlement. They nomination to the post of Miido Bulliang can be made either from priest or common man who have adequate knowledge on the subject. Both stratified section of the Apatani society i.e. Gyuth (patrician) and Gyuchi (plebeian) are eligible to be appointed for the post.

The Neya Bulliang has multifaceted works in judicial, social and religious sphere. The social works of the Neya Bulliang is to look after the general welfare of whole community. They act as an agency for developmental activities relating to construction of bunds on river side to prevent flood, construction of bridge over the canal, construction of roads & paths, decides the date of socio-religious ceremonies, monitor the maintenance of public property and so on. Above all they properly maintain peace and tranquility within their jurisdiction by maintain strict vigil on the society. In doing so, they lead and mobilize the village community for implementation of such activities.

The institution of Neya Bulliang have very elaborate role to play in the religious affairs of Apatani belief system. In almost all the ritual incantation the priest has to narrate a phrase in relation to the origin and role of Neya Bulliang. The priest also accepts that the purpose of solemnization will not redress the grievances

for which it was performed if above verses are not recited. Besides, they have a specific role to play during socio-religious ceremonies of Myoko, Murung and Subu Tanii.

Judicial administration is the main function of Neya Bulliangs of Apatani society. The Neya Bulliangs as the judicial council of the tribe and its members are the arbitrator and jurist. Their concept of tribal justice is strictly utilitarian. Preservation of social harmony, peace and equilibrium is the supreme aim of Neya Bulliangs. In theory, all form of disputes is settled by the Neya Bulliangs without bias and partiality to which the people respect and endorse it. However, man being the social animal, sometimes the decisions of the Neya Bulliangs is influenced because they sides their respective kinsmen if the plaintiff or dependent was one of them. Despite the fact, there the decision of the Neya Bulliangs is always honored and the sanctity of the institution is preserved. Though the Neya Bulliangs are the upholders of tribal justice, they never interfere in the dispute until or unless the dispute becomes a public issue. As a matter of fact when the disputes endanger the community peace, the Neya Bulliangs enter the field of action. Besides, the other option for entrusting Neya Bulliangs for settlement of dispute arises when the plaintiff approaches. Generally, The Neya Bulliangs deals with both civil and criminal cases.

When the dispute pertaining to both civil and criminal cases is referred to Neya Bulliangs, a date is fixed and both plaintiff and dependent are summoned along with their arbitrator. The venue for arbitration is fixed either in the house of plaintiff or dependent or in the public platform (Lapang). The Lapang (public platform) is the centre of administration of village and society. The trial and deliberation of arbitration and public discussion on developmental issue takes place in this sacred structure. Any adult male members of the society can participate and watch the proceeding. The Lapang (public platform) are massive chest high structure built of huge dead plants.

On the appointed day of arbitration, both parties are given ample scope to present the merits of their cases through an appointed arbitrator. The deliberation may take place for several days. Sometimes the trial of the cases carried forward for next date. These deliberations of arbitration are attended by the kinsmen of both the parties. However, normally the women do not participate or have any say until or unless she herself is party to the case. The presentation of merit points in the case should be supplemented by evidence, maxims and precedents. Finally, Neya Bulliangs based on the merits deliver the justice in accordance with customary laws. The loser of the arbitration is made to pay compensation to the winner appropriately. If the contestant agrees on the verdict of Neya Bulliangs, the case is closed for ever. Once the dispute is settled either of the contestant party is cautioned not to refer the dispute in near future.

The amicable judgment of the Neya Bulliangs on the case is followed with a ritual called Gensi Byapadu (purification ceremony) in the respective houses of both the contesting party²⁰. The purification ceremony is performed to appease the spirits for protection from dispute and controversy in the future. The solemnizing of this ritual may not necessarily be performed by a priest. It can be performed by a common person who has adequate knowledge of the subject since. The ritual requires long bacon which is burned in fire oven with brief incantation of sacred verses. This roasted bacon is cut into pieces and distributed amongst the arbitrator and meal is served to them. The verses of purification ritual are as follows:

Niihi Gomu Juhu Doko, Khallang Mimii Liike.

Khallang Mimii Ka Juhu Doko, Khangku Mimii Miishing Liike.

Koje Mullung Dadung Sili So, Butii Gomu Ka Juhu Doka.

Khallang Mimii Miishing Liike, Buchi Gomu Juhu Doko.

Niimi Ponju Miimi Miishing Liike.

(Gist: The verses intimate the spirit of disputes and controversy to remain cool since the issue has been settled and in anticipation we are offering you the roasted bacon and rice beer. These offerings are given to you for blessing the arbitrator in the settlement of the issue.)

The non-compliance of the verdict results into demonstration for penalty of fine called Dapo Sonii initiated by Neya Bulliangs. But when the verdict of the case is not acceptable to both the parties and verdict remains undecided due lack of evidences or sharp division on the opinion of Neya Bulliangs, the case is subjected to supernatural justice by the means of oath and ordeal.

In nutshell, Bulliangs are considered to be the upholder of customary laws and supreme authority in tribal justice with the sanction from supernatural entity. But the institution is diluted by establishment of parallel government institutions like goan buras and political interpreter. The major shares of works performed by the traditional institution are encroached. Today, the institution of bulliangs is left with mere religious responsibilities and more effectively exercise arbitration activities. The incumbent members of the traditional institution are left with no other option but to neglect their very existence. At present the traditional institutions like Kiimer Bulliang no longer exist, Kiidi and Mudo Bulliang are at the verge of extinction and Neya Bulliang exist but without any responsibility. This institution is the identity of the tribe that needs to be preserved and promoted. If they are empowered with the existed responsibilities under the government supervision, they are capable of upholding the peace and tranquility in the Apatani Plateau.

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